

Nitu

“Climate Change Impact: Evidences from Agriculture and Food Security in Coastal Areas in Khulna Region, Bangladesh”

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At present, Bangladesh is one of the most vulnerable to climate risk. It has been facing a great threat in the sector of agriculture and food security. Climate change adaptation policies are professed as a key sustainable development vision for Bangladesh. Being an agricultural country, climate change mostly affects the agricultural sector, damages crops, reduces the productivity and has the adverse impact on GDP. It is high time the climate change adaptation had been introduced. This paper aims to assess and forecast the impact of climate change in agriculture and food security of Koyra and Paikgachha upazila, Khulna. Almost 300 native and key stakeholders have been surveyed to collect the primary data (i.e. productivity, income, land, profit or loss and types of crops etc.). Secondary data (i.e. temperature, wind, humidity, rainfall, salinity, coastal flood, tropical cyclone, deforestation) have been collected from several government and non-government organizations like Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Center for Environmental and Geographic Information Services (CEGIS), etc. Geographic Information System (GIS) related software like-ArcGIS and several statistical softwares (IBM-SPSS, Spectrum) etc. have been used for analyzing and forecasting. Yet it is found salinity and cyclone Aila are the most impactful factors in this case and the magnitude of impact on livelihood also be found through the study. In future, this research will help to provide the innovative & technical solution for the adaptation of climate change in agriculture and food security aspect in coastal area.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change has become a burning global issue from twentieth century. The earth is now at its hottest state than ever before. The greenhouse gases i.e., different heat trapping gases are warming the globe, ozone layer is depleting, sea level is rising. The temperature of land and sea is continuously increasing. Inundation of lands, salinity, and insufficient water in dry seasons, flood is monsoons are adverse impact of climate change in agriculture. Population is increasing but the amount of arable land is decreasing to provide shelter for growing population. Little arable land but a huge pressure of cultivation to meet the need of people. This decreases the fertility of soil. Climate change is not purely a scientific problem rather human actions are more responsible for the warming. If the human behaved wisely, the warming would reduce or slow down (Urry, 2015). Climate change has a vast impact on physical, biological and socioeconomic sectors. The impact varies from region to region. Decline of forests, elevated concentration of CO₂, longer fire seasons, more frequent fires, change in hydrological cycle, altered precipitation and temperature, increased sediment loading and erosion, degraded shorelines, reduction of water quality and water supply, water pollution, air pollution, reduced stability of aquatic ecosystem, less severe winter, severity of insects and diseases, increase in water temperature, frequent floods and droughts due to rise of sea level, intrusion of saltwater, increase of wildfires and landslides, extreme weather events, increase of heat related mortality, exacerbated respiratory disorders, increased vector borne diseases are some of the impacts of climate change (Ball, et al., 1998).

Bangladesh is an agricultural country. Climate change impact is both beneficial and harmful as country's economy is dependent on agriculture. (Hossain, Arshad, Shahid, Fahad, & Akhter, 2019) Bangladesh is one of the most vulnerable to climate change (Agrawala, Ahmed, & U, 2003). It is in low-lying floodplains. It lies at the mouth of three river basins - the Brahmaputra, the Ganges and the Meghna (World Bank, 2010). There is already a sharp rise in temperature and change in rainfall patterns. (Shahid, 2010) The average daily temperature in Bangladesh has increased by 0.103°C per decade over the past four decades. (Shahid, 2010) The temperature of Bangladesh will continue to increase by 1°C by 2030, 1.4°C by 2050 2.4°C by 2100 as a result of global warming. (IPCC, 2010) This rising temperature will increase evaporation and air moisture holding capacity. It will change the annual and seasonal variability of rainfall. In Bangladesh more than 55% people depends on agriculture directly and 17.22% GDP comes from this sector (Hossain, Arshad, Shahid, Fahad, & Akhter, 2019). These impacts thus will affect them greatly.

In the coastal areas, coastal characteristics changes, salinized areas expand, intensity of salinity increases, drainage congestion and coastal flooding increases, cyclones and storm surges occur more frequently due to climate change (Sikder & Xiaoying, 2014). From the vulnerability index that has been prepared for the 7 unions of Koyra upazila of Bangladesh it has been found that southern and south western regions are more vulnerable than others. Two variabilities- water variability and infrastructure variability are being assessed by this index (Uddin, et al., 2019). Rice production fell because of climate change in coastal regions. Cyclone Sidr and Cyclone Aila affected on agriculture drastically (Rabbani, Rahman, Shoef, & Khan,

2015). Climate modeling is very important in climate researches, to make effective climate policies and various adaptive measures. Climate models have such importance because- 1) they serve as an important demonstration tool for policy makers 2) give an accurate calculation and prediction of future climatic events and possible impacts (Dastagir, 2015). This study attempts to assess the climate change impact on the sector of agriculture and food security. To forecast the impact on the sector of agriculture and food security.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Earlier, cyclone Sidr and Aila had hit hard on some villages of Khulna. The damage of Laxmikhola, Dacope upazila was most severe among others. Katianangla had faced less damage than Laxmikhola. Siltation is raising river height and this will increase more intrusion of salt water in crop land. In Laxmikhola, water salinity is more acute. New diseases and insect problems are rising that affect rice yields. (Rashid, et al., 2014)

In Shyamnagar upazila, Satkhira district 27% of 360 respondents suffered from a deficiency of food before 2011. The farmers mainly cultivate Aman during monsoon to early winter (June-December) there. They also cultivate other rice crop and vegetables during December-May. More than 80% households reported (year-2012) severe food crisis have affected them at least ten times in last ten years. Food shortage is increasing in this area as production of rice is low due to soil salinity, late rainfall, seasonal drought and excessive rainfall (Rabbani, Rahman, Shoef, & Khan, 2015).

Climate change poses a major soil salinization in coastal Bangladesh. In coastal areas 30% cultivable land is available where salinity is affected by tidal flooding during wet season, direct inundation by storm surges and movement of saline ground and surface water during dry season. According to soil salinity projections, Khulna and Bagerhat have highest median salinity, highest maximum salinity during dry seasons and highest maximum salinity during flooding seasons comparing others coastal areas of the country. Here, median salinity captures central tendency in annual salinity, maximum salinity during dry seasons assesses seasonally intense salinity on dry season crops particularly High Yielding Variety (HYV) Boro rice and maximum salinity during flooding seasons assesses intense salinity particularly paddy irrigated Aman rice. Annual median salinity (dS/m) for 2001, 2009, 2050 (low) and 2050 (high) are respectively for Mongla upazila, Bagerhat - 9.6, 10.7, 11.5 and 11.7 (dS/m); Paikgacha upazila, Khulna - 10.5, 12.7, 13.0, 13.0 (dS/m); Dumuria upazila, Khulna - 10.2, 11.9, 12.9, 13.2 (dS/m). Maximum soil salinity during dry (November-April) seasons (dS/m) for 2001, 2009, 2050 (low) and 2050 (high) are respectively for Mongla upazila, Bagerhat - 13.1, 17.3, 17.8, 18.0 (dS/m); Paikgacha upazila, Khulna - 11.6, 17.1, 17.0, 17.1 (dS/m); Batiaghata upazila, Khulna - 9.4, 17.2, 18.4, 19.2 (dS/m); Dumuria upazila, Khulna - 11.8, 15.7, 16.3, 16.6 (dS/m). Maximum soil salinity during wet (July-September) seasons (dS/m) for 2001, 2009, 2050 (low) and 2050 (high) are respectively for Mongla upazila, Bagerhat - 10.8, 10.6, 11.7, 11.9 (dS/m); Paikgachha upazila, Khulna - 9.9, 12.4, 12.6, 12.6 (dS/m); Batiaghata upazila, Khulna - 3.9, 7.5, 9.8, 10.6 (dS/m); Dumuria upazila, Khulna - 10.3, 11.9, 12.9, 13.1 (dS/m) (Dasgupta, Hossain, Huq, & Wheeler, 2015).

3. Materials and Methods

The primary data were collected mainly using Questionnaire survey by the interrogation of Paikgachha and Koyra upazila, Khulna local people (Table 01). As the population was known, finite sample size was estimated for sampling. But so far limitation, 300 native stakeholders was selected within random sampling. 150 households were taken from paikgachha upazila, khulna and 150 households was selected from Koyra upazila, Khulna).

Fig 01: Study area map of Paikgachha and Koyra upazilla, Khulna

(Source: Author, 2020)

Table 01: Socio Economic Characteristics of the Respondent Households

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	210	70
Female	90	30
Family size		
1-4	40	13
4-8	190	63
>8	70	24
Education level		
Elementary school	110	36
Junior high or middle school	80	27
High school	45	15
College/institute	65	22
Postgraduate	-	-
Monthly income		
>10,000	170	57
10-000-15000	45	15
15,000-25,000	65	22
>25,000	20	6

*(Source: Field survey, 2020)***Table 02: Land Categories Based on Flooding Pattern**

Type	Category	Flood Depth	Area (%)	Nature of flooding
F0	Highland((HL))	Not flooded	6%	Intermittent of flooded up to 30cm
F1	Medium highland(MH)	30-90 cm	17%	seasonal
F2	Medium lowland(ML)	90-180 cm	40%	seasonal
F3	Lowland(L)	Over 180 cm	28%	Seasonal(<9 months)
F4	Very lowland (VL)	Over 180 cm	7%	Seasonal(<9 months) or perennial

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Responses taken from the participants that were analyzed through ArcGIS, SPSS and Excel to visualize the actual scenario of the affected peoples' agro-economic life.

A diagram is displayed below to point out the analyzes done:

4. ANALYSIS

4.1 General People Perception on Climate Changes

Within time period, the local inhabitant was experienced in climate change impact in the dimension of agriculture and food security. 73% responded was agreed to increase in temperature in day by day and for this a massive impact was addressed on their cultivation.

Table 03: Perceived Knowledge on Climate Changes as Observed by Respondents

SL.No.	Perceived knowledge	Respondent Percentage (%)
1	Increase in temperature	73%
2	Increase more erosion	28%
3	Drought frequency has increase	3%
4	Increase erratic rainfall	62%
5	Getting warmer in climate	78%
6	Uncertainty in predicting the weather	65%
7	Changes in sea level(waves, tides and currents)	57%
8	Increase in the risk of crop failure	35%
9	Variation in year to year weather pattern	81%
10	Increase in storm surges, flooding and disaster	47%

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

The other remarkable perceived knowledge towards climate change type such as increase more erosion (28%), getting warmer in climate (78%), variation in year to year weather pattern (81%), increase in storm surges, flooding and disaster (47%).

Fig 02: Variation on climate changes as experienced by respondents

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Fig 03: Agricultural activities adaptation process in farmers

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Increase deforestation option was highly agreed by respondent (53%), maximum climate change impact section was agreed by stakeholder. Salinity problem was addressed by 48% local people of study area [fig 02]. The meaningful impact was also existing in agricultural general activities practices in farmers. The perception among farmers like as use of fertilizer increase in 88%, normal crop decrease in 48%, saline tolerate crop production was decreased in 66% [fig 03].

Fig 04: Victim's percentage among respondent due to natural disaster

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

This chart shows the percentages of the affected respondents is counted on various cyclones from 2005-2020. Many respondents claimed that their households, livestock and other belongings were damaged several times, that's why this research found some cases where a person responded for being damaged by cyclone SIDR, again the same person responded for being damaged by cyclone AILA or Amphan. This happened because of the geographical location of this two upazilla, as the locations are in disaster prone area.

4.2 Land Variation Impact on Climate Change

Table 04: Land Variation in Comparative Time Duration

Farmer's category	2005	2010	2015	2020
Large farmer (> 2 ha land)	30	16	38	23
Medium farmer (1-2 ha land)	72	19	65	45
Small (0.2-1.0 ha land)	163	177	158	137
Landless (homestead only)	35	88	39	95

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Table 05: Land Decrease for Climate Change

Farmer's category	2005 (Ha)	2010 (Ha)	2015 (Ha)	2020 (Ha)	Comment
Large farmer (> 2 ha land) (23 out of 100) avg. value-	3.5	3	2.5	2.2	Due to SIDR, Aila and Amphan, destroy of crops, land salinity, low growth rate of crops.
Medium farmer (1-2 ha land) (45 out of 100) avg. value-	3	2.5	2	1.8	Devastating Tidal boars, cyclones in 2006, 2009, 2020, acute salinity in fisheries and land, loss of profit due to cultivation.
Small (0.2-1.0 ha land) (23 out of 100)	2	1.5	1.2	0.8	Embankment breakage, frequent tidal bores washed away crops and, loss of revenues caused low per head income and

avg. value-					lack of interest in investing new land purchase.
Landless (homestead only) (23 out of 100)	1.2	1	.8	.5<	Frequent natural disasters made landless, foodless and shelter less.
avg. value-					

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Table 04 shows the amount of land through the passage of 2005 to 2020 farmers have owned. The occurrences caused by SIDR and AILA decreased the amount of owned land in the year 2010, as some large and farmers had to sell their land property to give back up their family expenditure, many small farmers had to become landless to earn livelihood by working as day laborer because agricultural sector in that time was not that profitable for being damaged by tidal bore and cyclones. Same things repeated in the year 2020 for cyclone Amphan and Covid-19 situation. Table 05 can be considered as the illustrated form of table 04, where relevant causes are mentioned.

4.3 Climate Change Impact on Crop Sector

Table 06 explains the scenario in of cultivation of various crops in different years. The average growth of each types of crops were moderate. But again for the attack of cyclone SIDR an AILA, the cultivation of crops was not very sufficient, that's why maximum respondent chose "bad" or "worse" option. Cyclone Amphan attacked these areas in 2020 which resulted in worse cultivation of crops again.

Table 06: The Impact on Crop Production (Good/Moderate/Bad/Worse)

Year	Food crops (wheat, maize, rice and potatoes)	Feed crops (barley, and grasses)	Fiber crops (hemp, cotton, bamboo)	Oil crops (sunflower, olives)	Ornamental crops (garden or pot flowers, bushes)	Industrial crops (rubber, betel leaf)
2005				No oil crops cultivation		
Good	102	185	98		163	189
Moderate	148	101	149	-	137	100
Bad	38	12	32	-	0	9
worse	12	2	21	-	0	2
2010				No oil crops cultivation		
Good	17	10	7		14	3
Moderate	23	13	22	-	23	13
Bad	138	201	134	-	167	127
worse	122	76	137	-	93	157

Year	Food crops (wheat, maize, rice and potatoes)	Feed crops (barley, and grasses)	Fiber crops (hemp, cotton, bamboo)	Oil crops (sunflower, olives)	Ornamental crops (garden or pot flowers, bushes)	Industrial crops (rubber, betel leaf)
2015				No oil crops cultivation		
Good	32	29	27		53	47
Moderate	107	115	116	-	139	129
Bad	98	79	138	-	100	98
worse	63	77	19	-	8	26
2020				No oil crops cultivation		
Good	17	15	16		23	119
Moderate	98	117	119	-	101	115
Bad	107	121	109	-	137	110
worse	78	47	56	-	39	56

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Table 06 explains the scenario in of cultivation of various crops in different years. The average growth of each types of crops were moderate. But again for the attack of cyclone SIDR an AILA, the cultivation of crops was not very sufficient, that's why maximum respondent chose "bad" or "worse" option. Cyclone Amphan attacked these areas in 2020 which resulted in worse cultivation of crops again.

Fishing sector:

Fisheries were highly damaged by SIDR, AILA and Amphan. Tidal bore, acuteness of saline water and break out of fishery embankments caused a great loss in 2010 and 2020 respectively. Table 07 shows the damage through participated dwellers' point of view.

Table 07: The Impact on Fishing Sector

Categories	2005	2010	2015	2020	comment
Cultivation land					
<10 bigha	54%	79%	59%	76%	
11-20 bigha	23%	10%	18%	12%	Due to Devastating cyclones in 2006, 2009, 2019.
12-30 bigha	11%	5%	10%	8%	
31-40 bigha	9%	3%	9%	3%	

Categories	2005	2010	2015	2020	comment
>40 bigha	3%	3%	4%	1%	2020 tidal boar and Covid-19 situation.
Production per year					
1 metric ton	47%	82%	47%	85%	2010's impact was worse than 2005. The situation updated gradually in 2015
2-3 metric ton	27%	9%	22%	8%	
3-4 metric ton	15%	7%	16%	1%	
4-5 metric ton	7%	2%	11%	6%	
>5 metric ton	4%	0%	4%	0%	
Virus					
all season	12%	16%	14%	11%	But again for cyclone Bulbul, Amphan and Covid-19, situation in 2020 is Bad again.
sometimes	60%	69%	71%	83%	
rare	28%	15%	15%	16%	
Loss 50 k/year	67%	29%	59%	23%	
50-1 lakh/year	23%	27%	26%	21%	
1-3 lakh/year	8%	32%	10%	39%	
>4 lakh/year	2%	12%	5%	17%	

(Source: Field

survey, 2020)

Livestock Sector:

This table shows the circumstances of livestock owning from 2005 to 2020. People loss their cattle, poultries, dairy farms and other live stocks for devastating cyclones like SIDR (2006), AILA (2009), Bulbul (2019) and Amphan (2020) etc. Live stocks are great sources of incomes; which's loss bring out economic crisis as well as food insecurity also.

Table 08: The climate change impact on Livestock Sector

categories	2005	2010	2015	2020	comment
Beef cattle	28%	23%	26%	28%	Many of the families have cattle, goat, and poultry together at a time.
Goat	36%	38%	42%	39%	
Horse	6%	1%	0	0	
Poultry	87%	72%	89%	83%	

	Sheep	12%	9%	14%	11%	
Disease	Sometimes	75%	58%	55%	65%	Sometimes, diseases broke out in an epidemic form.
	Almost	17%	39%	32%	28%	
	rare	8%	3%	23%	7%	
Interested	Low	11%	34%	28%	27%	Maximum people had moderate interest.
	Medium	57%	56%	62%	65%	
	High	32%	10%	10%	8%	
Cause	Disaster	37%	59%	49%	56%	Main causes are disasters and lack of land property to accommodate livestock's.
	Global Warming	12%	2%	15%	8%	
	Lack of land	50%	38%	34%	30%	
	Deforestation	1%%	1%	2%	6%	

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Figure 05 shows the main responsible factors for decreasing crop production. Maximum respondents agreed that salinity is the most responsible reason for low production of crops. Figure 06 shows the tendency of food cultivation among the farmers of study area. It indicates that after the attack of SIDR and AILA, the trend of food cultivation decreased and the influence of low food production still had remained in 2010. After the attack of Amphan in 2020, and also for Covid-19 situation, the trend of food cultivation again decreased because of damage of agricultural land, economic crisis and less demand of food etc.

Fig 05: Cause of decrease of crop production

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Fig 06: Trend of food production

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

4.4 Food Security

The following table shows the percentages among the respondents, who were able to cultivate their food from their own land, fisheries, yards and gardens. Maximum families have a surety to have meals in two times in a day, and having options to grow vegetables for own needs in their yards. Most of the respondents owned even minimum amount of chickens or ducks to meet up the need of meat and eggs.

Table 09: Availability of Food (own housing)

Type	2005	2010	2015	2020
Have 3-time meal	78%	65%	70%	68%
Having 2time meal	23%	31%	28%	30%
Having 1 time	9%	4%	2%	2%
Vegetable cultivation in yards	67%	67%	71%	69%
Fishing source	42%	38%	47%	43%
Livestock (poultry, cow)	71%	63%	69%	69%
Availability of fruits	41%	37%	40%	39%

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Table 10: The Relation between Household Heads Level of Education and Food Security

Table 10, 11 and 12 is displayed to visualize the relatable factors, which cause food insecurity. In table 10, it is clear that the persons with least education faced most insecurity for food. Table 11 shows that the landless people are the ultimate sufferers of food insecurity, as they do not even owe minimum amount of land to cultivate crops for themselves. These landless farmers are the daily wage earners who works in other people's field, which is shown in table 12. And irony of fate is, these poor people are suffering most in food insecurity problem by profession also.

Highest grade by household head	% Food Insecure
Primary or less (1-5 years)	43%
Secondary or less (6-10 years)	27%
Higher secondary or less (11-12 years)	19%
Graduate or less(13-16 years)	11%

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Table 11: The Relation between Land Size and Food Insecurity

Land size	% Food Insecure
Landless<0.05acre	37%
Functionally landless0.05-0.5 acre	29%
Marginal 0.5-1.5 acres	21%
Small 1.5-2.4	11%
Medium or large2.5 acres or more	2%

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

Table 12: The Relation between Employment Type and Food Security

Employment type	% Food Insecure
Daily wage(agro)	30%
Self-employed(agro)	23%
Daily wage(non-agro)	25%
Self-employed(non-agro)	12%
Wage employment(non-agro)	10%

(Source: Field survey, 2020)

4.5 Economical loss Due to Climate Change

The following table shows the economic scenarios in agricultural sector from 2005 to 2020. The attack of two super cyclones, SIDR and AILA, brought out damage and miseries which were followed by 2010 also. Again, cyclone Amphan is responsible for the deterioration of this' years agro-economic condition. So natural disasters are very prime factors to make a mark in these areas' economic profile.

Table 13: Climate change Impact on Economic Sector

Type of crop	Sector	2005	2010	2015	2020
Average Investment/yr.(tk) (average= total investment/no. of respondents)	Farming	20,000	18,000	23,700	
	Fishing	17,200	11,300	22,090	
	Livestock	19,000	12,080	18,000	
Average profit/yr (tk) (average= total profit/no. of respondents)	Farming	20450	15010	35540	
	Fishing	17500	13320	95650	
	Livestock	26080	14520	78050	
Average loss/yr (tk) (average= total loss/no. of respondents)	Farming	6700	9120	11790	
	Fishing	7320	10010	23370	Running Year
	Livestock	7890	8120	18290	
Import in a year (%)	Farming	21%	35%	24%	
	Fishing	75%	62%	81%	
	Livestock	4%	3%	5%	
contribution to GDP%	Farming	7%	11%	9%	
	Fishing	90%	82%	88%	
	Livestock	3%	7%	3%	

(Source: Author, 2020)

Through Asian development bank, poverty line of Bangladesh is 1.90 \$/day. In 2010's prospect, 169 people among our 300 respondents were living below the poverty line, as per day income was less than 1.90 \$. This happened because of the devastating attack of two cyclones, SIDR (2006) and Aila (2009). Sectors of income were reduced and failure in crop production as well as loss in fisheries were the causes of producing households living under poverty line.

Fig 07: Variation through per day income BDT

(Source: Author, 2020)

This means, the monthly savings of people in areas attacked by cyclones and tidal bores are negatively highly correlated with the degree of vulnerability of disasters upon them. Low vulnerable areas' people are quite eligible to save a handsome amount per month, but people of highly vulnerable areas are not even capable to meet up their daily needs, so savings per month are less important factor to them, and this point indicates more unpredictable future and

sustainability of the people because they do not have economic backups to survive against further hazardous situations.

This research sorted out most damaged 40 households after SIDR and AILA attack. 20 households were selected from each upazilla. In this table, value of less than 0.05, which proves the means of each factors are different from each other. Again, according to t distribution table, for 95% significance and N=40, $t = 1.684$, so the value of t in the table is greater than distribution table's value of t. So from this paired sample t-test, the point of view is clear, which explains that the economic misery of these people were caused by the attack of those two cyclones within a short interval.

Table 14: Bivariate Correlation

Variables	Standard Deviation	Means	Value of R
Degree of Vulnerability due to Disaster on people	0.846	1.80	-0.781
Monthly Savings of the People of vulnerable areas	940.816	962.7199	

(Source: Author, 2020)

Table 15: Paired T-test of Income before SIDR and Aila and Income after SIDR and Aila

Compared Paired Factors	Mean		Std. Deviation	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Income Before SIDR and AILA	Income after SIDR and AILA		Lower	Upper		
Income Before SIDR and AILA and Income after SIDR and AILA	3137.500	2575.00	611.71784	366.86314	758.13686	5.816	.000

(Source: Author, 2020)

7.6 Forecast (Land less Farmer and Food Insecurity in Study Area)

According to the 300 respondents, the percentages of the affected people is counted on various cyclones from 2005-2020.

Fig 08: Extrapolation of land less farmer

(Source: Author, 2020)

Within the scheme of 2005-2020, the research tried to find out the portion of landless farmers in study area and tried to give a prediction through forecasting collected data. Forecasting on people who have to buy rice for eating instead of growing rice in their agricultural land because of shortage of land and investment.

Fig 09: Food insecurity (purchasing rice in spite of cultivation in own land)

(Source: Author, 2020)

5. DISCUSSION

The study areas named Koyra and Paikgacha upazila of Khulna district. Among the respondent the highest number of population range between 31-40 years (37%). Maximum highest level of education is primary level (32%). 40% is medium low land which is subjected to seasonal flooding. 78% people think the climate is getting warmer and 73% think the temperature is rising. 81% people acknowledged

the variation in yearly weather pattern. In 2020, the number of small land farmers is the highest and large farmers is the lowest. From 2005 to 2020, food crops yielding deteriorated drastically. Same case goes with feed crops, fiber crops and industrial crops. Major reason behind this massive decrease in crop production is salinity (42%). Because of the disasters and lack of land, animal husbandry is decreasing or is not enough for the rising population. In 2015, investment in fishing sector has increased relatively and GDP in this sector has increased (88%). Food consumption is relatively low in 2020 than 2005. There has been found a strong relation between education level of the household head and food insecurity, land size and food insecurity and employment and food insecurity. Most people strongly agreed the impact of climate change on the availability of fresh water. Saline tolerant crop production, use of pesticides and introduction of technology in irrigation have increased. Amphan affected mostly Satkhira and then Khulna district. Here, bivariate correlation value was -0.781 , that means the monthly savings of people in areas attacked by cyclones and tidal bores are negatively highly correlated with the degree of vulnerability of disasters upon them. As these areas geographically disaster prone, the socioeconomic condition of these people is continuously disrupted and declining.

6. CONCLUSION

The impact of climate change in agriculture and food security is ascending vastly. In the coastal areas soil salinity and water salinity is increasing due to sea level rise, natural disasters, etc. Again, the weather pattern is changing every year. Flood washes away huge amount of crop every year causing a great harm to human and animal lives. In Khulna district, the worst scenario is in Koyra and Paikgacha. The socioeconomic condition is miserable. People are losing lands, soil fertility is decreasing, salinity increasing, inundation of lands, increased floods and droughts these are deteriorating their livelihood. A proper resilient plan is needed particularly for these areas as their living condition is constantly hampered for the disasters. Adaptive measures have to be taken to control the floods and salinity to make these areas more productive and reduce the sufferings of the people.

7. REFERENCE

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